

CDM provides a much needed higher tier, validated, and open-source arable crop spray drift model for regulatory risk assessment

The Casanova Drift Model (CDM): an arable crop spray drift deposition model

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Why do we need CDM?

- Today's pesticide risk assessments rely either on drift tables or screening levels models that result in excessively large, unrealistic buffer zones
- Field studies provide real-world exposure assessment but are limited because they can capture only selected application and environmental parameters
- A higher-tier arable crop drift deposition model is needed that is validated, open-source, and has a user-friendly accessible interface

What does CDM have?

A user-friendly web-based user interface is being developed in combination with an open-source code repository to enable regulatory risk assessments and transparency to model algorithms

How good is CDM?

Successful validation against SETAC DRAW and SDTF datasets

